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may be due to the phytotoxicity of the herbicide molinate, which from observation decreased plant population and development. This reduced development led to flowering during low air temperatures and to high spikelet sterility. The other treatments gave better red rice control and therefore higher crop yields.

In the second year, treatments T1 and T4 resulted in lower rice grain yields due to poor weed control. On the other hand, treatments where seeding was done on inundated soil resulted in better red rice control and higher rice yield. Table 2 shows

the number of seeds per square meter in each of three evaluations, and the change in seed bank size as a percentage of viable seeds in the soil after each treatment (based on initial quantity). In the first cropping year, T1, T2, and T3 increased the soil seed bank, whereas T4 decreased it. Other treatments contributed to a decrease in the seed bank in the soil. A reduced seed bank in treatments that used inundated soil (T5, T6, and T7) was likely due to lesser new seeds in the soil and lower germination because anaerobic soil caused a higher loss rate in red rice seeds. On the other hand, for treatments T9, T10,

and T11, reduced red rice seeds was due to no new seeds added to the soil and loss of viability of older seeds through time.

In conclusion, among treatments tested to establish lowland rice, the highest grain yields were observed in treatments that control red rice when rice is established in flooded land. Treatments using crop rotation with sorghum, summer tillage, fallow, and rice seeding in flooded soil are the most efficient in reducing red rice seed banks.

Identifying and grading limiting factors of upland rice yields in farmers' fields of northern Thailand

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In peninsular Southeast Asia, swidden cultivation of upland rice is still an important component of remote highland farming systems. Also, yields in farmers' fields are generally low (1–1.5 t ha⁻¹) but very variable under no-external-input cropping systems. Yields of 3 and 4 t ha⁻¹ for early and late local varieties, respectively, are observed in pockets in the field (Van Keer et al 1998). But such yields are seldom reached due to the multiple interacting limiting factors characteristic of such an unfavorable rice ecosystem. Identifying and ranking these limiting factors is a prerequisite to setting research and extension priorities for improving current farmers' practices to reduce yield gaps.

An on-farm diagnostic survey, covering a very extensive range of upland rice crop situations, was carried out during 1993–96 in Mae-Haeng, a Lahu highland village of Fang District, Chiang Mai Province, in upper northern Thailand (600–800 m asl). The objectives were to characterize the upland rice crop

population, environmental conditions, and farmers' practices along the whole crop cycle; and to identify, date, and rank the main environmental and cropping system variables causing major yield limitations under farmers' circumstances and management practices.

Data on crop population status for two early and late-maturing types of local cultivars, crop environmental conditions, and cropping practices were obtained every 2 wk from 432 squares (1 m² each). These squares were delimited at crop emergence to 63, often sloping, farmers' fields of deep granitic soils with a clay-loamy texture and medium chemical fertility. To identify and to rank causes of rice yield differentiation, a principal component analysis with instrumental variables (PCAIV, Lebreton et al 1991) was carried out on the 1993–96 pooled data, and for individual year subdatasets.

PCAIV allows, for the same number of *n* individual entities (here, *n*=432), the simultaneous analysis of two multivariate data matrices, i.e., a dependent matrix,

made in this case of upland rice crop population characteristics (yield and successive components of yield), and an independent matrix comprising all the measured crop environmental and management variables. First, simultaneous multiple regressions for each variable of the dependent crop population data matrix on all variables of the independent crop environment and management matrix are carried out. After this step, a new matrix is obtained presenting the part of the crop population characteristics explained by the crop environment and management data. In the second step, classic principal component analysis (PCA) is done on this new matrix. In the on-farm agronomic survey, for both pooled data and individual years, relatively high levels were obtained for the percentage of inertia of the first two axes and for the pertinence of the PCAIV.

For the reproductive phase, the analysis of the upland rice yield buildup processes (Wey et al 1998) pinpointed panicle formation and spikelet differentiation as key periods of yield

differentiation. During the vegetative period, poor crop biomass accumulation was also found to be more important than low plant density. Vegetative biomass accumulation per plant influenced panicle and spikelet formation, but not spikelet fertilization or grain filling (data not shown).

The analysis of pooled data (see figure) reveals strong negative relationships for (a) number of panicles plant⁻¹ and number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ vs rice root aphid infestation; (b) plant density vs late weed competition and late-maturing cultivars (with lower sowing densities); and (c) percentage of filled spikelets and 1,000-grain weight vs 1995 wet season, which was characterized by dry spells during the reproductive phase. Weak negative relationships were found for number of panicles plant⁻¹ vs slope angle, erosion, number of successive upland rice crops, minimum tillage, and early weed stress. A rather weak positive correlation between the older forest type of fallow and upland rice grain yield was also observed. Brown spot was the only disease with limited importance, especially on late-maturing varieties.

The analysis of the major and minor limiting factors of yield and its components for individual year subdatasets summarized in the table isolated rice root aphid infestation as the single major limiting factor with a strong and consistent effect on final upland rice grain yields. Weed competition during the vegetative phase of the crop cycle was found to be the second most important yield-limiting factor, followed by soil erosion in sloping fields after tillage. It was only in one out of four cropping seasons that the last two upland rice yield components were negatively affected by drought.

Results of this on-farm agronomic survey support the validity of several common hypotheses on limiting factors in upland rice (weed competition, drought stress, soil erosion). That no very significant soil nutrient-limiting factor was diagnosed could be due to the fact that the survey was carried out on a soil type with a relatively high level of chemical

Plane of PCAIV first two axes showing the relationships between upland rice yield, components of yield, crop environmental conditions, and crop management practices in Mae Haeng Village, Chiang Mai Province, Thailand, pooled data for 1993-96. Crop growth variables (measured at harvest): PL = no. of plants m⁻²; PAPL = no. of panicles plant⁻¹; SPPA = no. of spikelets panicle⁻¹; % FSP = percentage of filled spikelets; WTG = 1000-g weight; YIELD = grain yield. Crop environmental and management variables: ec, lc = early, late cultivars; mt, dt = minimum, deeper tillage; yc = no. of successive years of upland rice cultivation; ff, bf, gf = forest, bamboo, grass fallows; ws1, ws2, ws3, ws4 = 1993, 1994, 1995, 1996 wet seasons; sl = slope angle; er = severity of soil erosion; sand = percentage of sand; ph = pH; som = soil organic matter; pav = available P; camg = soil Ca + Mg content; k = soil K content; we1, we2 = cumulated area under the weed cover curve for 0-60 DAS and for 60 DAS to harvest, respectively; bs = degree of brown spot infestation; ra = degree of rice root aphid infestation.

fertility. It is also possible that the standard static soil fertility measurements used in the survey were not sufficient to identify meaningful relationships with crop population characteristics. Finally, this analysis showed that close attention should be paid to soil-borne upland rice pests when prioritizing issues for improving upland rice-based cropping systems in the northern Thailand highlands.

References

Lebreton JD, Sabatier R, Banco G, Bacou AM. 1991. Principal component and correspondence analyses with respect to instrumental variables: an overview of their

roles in studies of structure-activity and species-environment relationships. In: Applied multivariate analysis in SAR and environment studies, ECSC, EEC, EAEC, Brussels and Luxembourg. p 85-114.
 Van Keer K, Trebuil G, Courtois B, Vejpas C. 1998. On-farm characterization of upland rice varieties in north Thailand. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 23(3): 21-22.
 Wey J, Oliver R, Manichon H, Siband P. 1998. Analysis of local limitations to maize yield under tropical conditions. *Agronomie* 18:545-561.

Major and minor factors and conditions influencing upland rice yield buildup based on results of PCAIV analysis for each cropping year in Mae Haeng Village, Chiang Mai Province, Thailand, 1993-96. Boldface indicates strongest relationships.^a

Year	1993 WVS		1994 WVS		1995 WVS		1996 WVS		1993-96 WVS	
	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+
No. of plants m ⁻²	lc ^a er we1, we2 mt, sl	ec sand, dt	we2, lc we1 yc, ff	ec	ra, we2 we1 er, yc		we1, we2 camg k, yc lc	ec	we2 lv	ec dt
No. of panicles plant ⁻¹	ra we1, we2 camg ph, bf mt, sl k	sand, dt	er k ra, bs camg pav		ra, we2 gf er, yc we1		er ra sl/mt camg k, yc	dt	ra ws3 er, sl we1, we2 yc mt	ff
No. of spikelets panicle ⁻¹	ra we1, we2 camg ph, bf mt, sl	ff	er k ra, bs camg pav		ec gf, lc ra, we2	camg sl	ra mt er		ra ws3 ec er, sl yc	
% filled spikelets	ec	lc			ws3 ec gf	camg lc			ws3 ec	lc ws2
1,000-grain weight					ws3 lc we1	ec			ws3 ec	lc ws2
Inertia of axes 1-2	84%		87%		70%		75%		84%	
Pertinence of PCAIV	63%		67%		52%		79%		37%	

^aSee figure for abbreviations of variables.

Instructional videos available

The Leaf Color Chart (LCC) (8:20 min)

Farmers generally observe the color of rice leaves to determine a rice crop's need for nitrogen fertilizer. Dark green rice leaves mean a high nitrogen content, while pale green rice leaves necessitate the application of more nitrogen fertilizer.

Mere observation, however, holds no absolute guarantee in measurement accuracy. Thus, to better help farmers determine their rice crops' need for nitrogen, the Leaf Color Chart (LCC) was developed.

The *Leaf Color Chart (LCC)* instructional video was produced to familiarize farmers and extension workers with the proper use of this new and affordable farming implement.

Portable chlorophyll meter for nitrogen management in rice (13:30 min)

In agriculture, excess nitrates can actually be highly damaging to crops and the environment. There is, thus, a need to efficiently manage the application of nitrogen fertilizers on rice crops.

The *Portable Chlorophyll Meter for Nitrogen Management in Rice* introduces the features and use of the chlorophyll or SPAD meter which is capable of measuring the relative nitrogen content in plant leaves through a simple, quick, and nondestructive procedure.

Go break into the code (13:30 min)

Genetic engineering need not be a property of the scientific few. This is what IRRI had in mind when it produced *Go breAk inTo the Code*: to make the general public grasp and understand the seemingly complicated science through a visually stunning, fast-paced, and entertaining presentation about the genetic code, DNA sequencing, and plant biotechnology.

The video also gives the public a glimpse as to how IRRI scientists are redesigning the rice plant—that most important food staple, using biotechnology tools.

These instructional videos are available in English, in the 3/4-inch u-matic and VHS formats, and in the NTSC, SECAM, or PAL systems.

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